

Cyber Personhood

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

In early 2020, the rapid adoption of remote and communication tools by governments, businesses and individuals around the world increased their reliance on cyber infrastructure for the normal functioning of countries, businesses and businesses. And in some parts of society, the urgent need for communication, while protecting human life, takes precedence over ensuring that these communication tools are safe and resilient. However, the question is raised as to whether these tools should be considered important infrastructure or more important, depending on their tight inclusion in everyday life around the world.

In many countries, the important importance of the environment to sustain human life has been recognized by extending the legal personality, or legal rights, to the environmental entity. Countries like Colombia, Ecuador, New Zealand and India have generally granted legal rights to various rivers, lakes, parks and nature. This article explores future possibilities and examples, allowing the country to consider granting legal rights to other very important institutions that are unrecognized. Human Life Looking to the future of becoming increasingly dependent on highly interdependent systems in cyberspace, could these systems be personalized?

The impact of remote operations and cybersecurity can lead to a whole new perception of the importance of cyberspace dependence and, as a result, new legal treatment. Against the backdrop of extensive debate on cyberspace legislation, including the law of war, this is a more complex legal consideration, especially in the light of cross-border dependencies and systems affecting multiple jurisdictions. Is to raise.

Through cyber biomimetics, this white paper adopts a blue-sky conceptual approach to study policy considerations and potential impacts when highly interdependent cyber systems in the distant future receive the same protection as environmental factors.

Keywords: CYBER PERSONHOOD, ENVIRONMENTAL PERSONHOOD, CYBER-ATTACK, HIGHLY INTERDEPENDENT CYBER SYSTEM

Introduction

Rivers, parks and other natural resources that life depends on Canada and US environmental law do not stand in their respective courts of jurisdiction. Standing instead, they harmed these natural features and injured humans. But what if natural resources are widely recognized in court and have legal rights, and injuries to these natural resources, along with the victim, are found in a crime?

If so, it may be presumed that there is a distant future in which highly interdependent resources in the cyberspace on which life depends are also recognized, but this is also a dynamic system that stands for the court to recognize. It is based on that.

That injury? This concept seems unlikely, as did the idea of environmental personality decades ago, and is a reality today. The idea that nations give cyber personalities to future cyber systems that are highly interdependent in a world where our dependence on cyber systems is increasing can be a logical evolution of some current trends.

This white paper explores the environmental personality and how a few countries have given it to specific natural resources. Through examples, we explain the term "cyber personality", match it with the precedent set by the environmental personality, present cyber personality candidates, and identify where cyber personality is not applicable and where it can be applied.

Finally, we consider the specific policy considerations and potential implications of cyber personality and consider broad adoption of this concept.

To the reader to understand what is described in this white paper

(1) Looking into the distant future in order to visualize highly interdependent cyber systems (2) Current cyber systems are not considered as cyber personality candidates. To standardize discussions in politics, policy, law and technology, we present the following definitions.

1. Cyberspace: "Physical and non-physical A component that stores, modifies, and exchanges data using a computer network. "

2. Cyber Infrastructure: "Communications, Storage, and Computing Devices The information system is built and operates. "

3. Important infrastructure: "Physical or virtual machines and assets in very important countries Its neutralization or destruction can undermine national security. Economy, public health, safety and environment. "

"Infrastructure administrators who own assets, systems, and networks, It is considered very important to United, whether physical or virtual. Its neutralization or destruction Security, national economic security, nation Public health, safety or a combination of these. "

4. Cyber System: "Multiple interconnected computers connected Software and peripherals. Here, the sensor and /or(programmable) Logic) controller, connected via computer network. Computer system General purpose (eg laptop) or special (eg "Blue Force" Tracking system "

5. Highly interdependent future cyber systems: In the next section.

Highly interdependent cyber systems

We are at stake in the future, already heavily dependent on major cybers. In some, governments, societies, businesses and individuals It cannot work without a case. Current trends show that these dependencies of always-on, always-reliable cyber systems are exacerbated. If you can't control it remotely during a coronavirus epidemic, more businesses have failed and more individuals who depend on the service have suffered. In the

spring of 2020, governments and businesses sought to increase the capacity of secure remote access and adopt remote voice and video communication methods. In some cases, these voice and video communication systems rely on a complex combination of in-house systems, service providers, cloud hosting providers and Internet access for their place of residence. This delicate balance of service delivery is an example of an existing dependency of a cyber system that is always up and running and always stable, depending on the availability of each internal service component. The roles and responsibilities so far are clear.

A near-future example to prove this includes a system that relies heavily on time signals that are fully synchronized with fully autonomous vehicles (without steering wheel). It wakes up in the morning and schedules the day, as well as digital identification and encryption to connect to common services in cyberspace. The roles and responsibilities of the systems of these technologies begin to be ambiguous as they depend on all time. For example, given that satellite-time signals can be manipulated or interrupted, 6 common time-dependent services such as map location and identity and certificate expiration that affect encryption. May not work as intended. Illustrated in the example, these temporary effects indicate that they can harm the operation of the system based on the synchronized time signal.

In addition, future societies can rely on emerging-based cyber systems. Current Status of Complex Theoretical Systems, 7 or Cyber Physical Systems / Management Completely human-created by an artificial intelligence (A1) system the system's algorithms are regularly rebuilt by the learning process of the system itself. The closer the cyber system is to emotions, the more rational it is to treat it to a legal entity with its own rights, which not only can be harmed, but can also make damaging decisions independent of human input.

Consider that some of these future cyber systems are now highly interdependent with each other, supplying and receiving data from each other and consuming each other's deeply nested computing power. These systems are managed by businesses and governments and, like many other systems today, can be potentially mis designed by individuals (as well as many commercial and packaging).

Roles and responsibilities that were once complex are becoming complex. In the future, countries (or some) that will provide medical services or maintain international obligations if these highly interdependent cyber systems become temporarily unavailable or severely damaged. It may affect the capacity of the country) and disrupt the economy. Induces public anxiety. As you read this article, if you want to match the description of highly interdependent cyber systems with the Critical National Infrastructure or match the software and / or services currently available, take a much closer look: Please try. Set up adjustments for currently existing services separately.

In the next section, examples of future highly interdependent cyber systems to navigate the positions taken by the country in relation to environmental personalities, coordinate this behavior in the future, and discuss cyber personalities. Considered the definition of the base.

Environmental personhood

It's easy to understand a company that has its rights as a legal entity. These legal entities can enter into contracts and own property and can be recognized as legal entities in court. However, in addition to businesses,

personality rights have been granted to natural resources in certain countries.

The germination of environmental personality is recorded in Christopher D. Stone's 1972 treatise, "Do Trees Need to Stand? Towards the Legal Rights of Natural Objects." This treatise proposes to grant legal rights to rivers, seas, forests and natural environmental systems. He recalled when the company was unable to discuss the rights of women and others. He explained how businesses do not have the same rights as legal entities, or certain people, such as prisoners and children, have limited rights. He argued that "legal rights holders" must meet all three criteria:

1. "[They] can take legal action upon request."
2. "In deciding to approve legal remedies, the court
With their [them] account, and "
3. "The slogan must be carried out for the benefit of [they]."

Stone suggested that these systems in the natural environment would be assigned legal guardians who could defend the rights of these systems. In his blue-sky treatise, he proposed not only rights, but also debt, using the example of a trust fund to compensate those affected by the floods.

Since Stone's treatise, some countries have adopted environmental personalities in different ways, switching slightly from a human-centric perspective to a biological-centric perspective. Several treatises have been published on the interpretation and challenges of state law on environmental personality.

Here is an example:

- Bangladesh: In 2019 Bangladesh assigned a legal guardian to the National River Conservation Commission, granting legal personality rights to all rivers.
- Bolivia: In 2010, Bolivia granted legal personality rights, a living system that passed the "Law on Mother Earth Rights" (Ley de Derechos de la Madre Tierra).
- Colombia: In 2016, the Constitutional Court of Colombia granted legal personality rights to the Rio Artrat basin under the joint guidance of the government and indigenous communities residing in the basin. 18 In 2018, the Supreme Court of Colombia recognized Amazon's rights. A unique decision has been reached involving multiple stakeholders to protect the life and health of the River and its surrounding ecosystem, the Amazonas Colombian in Colombia.
- Ecuador: The Ecuadorian Constitution, which led the allegations in 2008, has the right to "continue, maintain and regenerate, exist in the process of life cycle, structure, function and evolution" "Mother Recognize the legal personality of "Nature" (Panchamama). Anyone can petition on her behalf.
- India: In 2017, the Uttarakhand High Court of India granted the Ganges Yamuna River legal personality rights to its respective strong tree glaciers and sloppy Notry glaciers, as well as 21 other natural objects in Uttarakhand. Derived from. At the end of the year, the Indian Supreme Court postponed the Uttarakhand High Court's 2017 ruling. 22 March 2020 Punjab and Haryana High Court grant Sukhna Lake personality rights.
- New Zealand: New Zealand has granted legal personality rights to Te Urewera National Park in 2014, Whanganui River in 24 2017, and Mount Taranaki in 2017, legal to 26 Crowns, Whanganui and 8 Maori tribes.

A guardian has been assigned, respectively.

We know that, with the exception of India, these countries are not globally recognized in the legal view that defines them. With the exception of Ecuador and Bolivia, we also acknowledge that not all aspects of the living environment are entitled to a joint venture, only certain rivers, forests and parks. For this reason, environmental personality may be included in customary international law, or in the absence of rules of international law.

Instead of exploring the legal structure developed to create the concept of environmental personality, this white paper examines the distant future in which some countries confer personality rights on highly interdependent cyber systems. It is based on an established concept. We provide a cyber personality is the framework of this standard.

Cyber personhood

Our paper grants the legal personality rights of highly interdependent cyber systems in a manner similar to that of countries in the distant future granting environmental personalities to specific systems of the natural environment. It suggests that you can consider granting. Like the environmental personality, the rights and responsibilities of these cyber systems vary from system to system and are likely to be.

We provide the following definitions of cyber personality: Highly interdependent cyber systems by granting the rights of corporations of highly interdependent cyber systems under the legal framework. Has legal status to claim injuries and is responsible for all possible injuries resulting from it.

The concept of giving a legal personality to a computer-based system can look radical and exotic today, but far less than the idea for an environmental personality in 1972. Environmental problems are developing much faster in industry, politically motivated interests, and reliance on cyber systems. If the environmental personality takes more than 35 years to sit down in Ecuador, the cyber personality will reach appropriate legal changes to recognize or reject new realities, reflecting the rate of acceptance of the cyber system. You can significantly reduce the time required for this.

A. Cyber person candidate

Like corporate corporations or prisoners, future systems with high interdependence can belong to their own categories that require other treatments, including aspects of rights and obligations, as well as forms of ownership and supervision. I will. To help you understand the types of systems that can be considered cyber personalities, we have categorized them as follows: For each scenario, our focus remains on future highly interdependent cyber systems, states and their societies unable to function without them, and the existing legal structure that can be applied. Essentially invalidates the cyber personality concept of the first two candidates.

1. Privately owned cyber systems (personal): Many people provide homes with connections between home devices such as computers, mobile devices, and TVs and fringe devices such as refrigerators, toasters, coffee makers, and doors. I have a large network. Internet of Things objects for locks and other things. This candidate does not have a highly interdependent cyber system, but can be affected if it relies on an upstream highly interdependent cyber system that is no longer available. Nevertheless, if the services in this example are not available, the owner can claim damages that do not seriously affect the functional

capabilities of the state government. We don't think such personal systems are candidates for cyber personality.

2. Corporate and state-owned cyber systems (single institutions): These systems are necessary for corporate and state institutions to run their day-to-day businesses, and if they become unavailable, their impact on operations Limited. Damage to these systems can be claimed by the owner and damages to the system can be paid by the owner, so cyber personality may not be granted.
3. Manifold-owned cyber systems with a single jurisdiction: In this case, companies in some countries with or without state-owned systems can use their cyber services to simply service highly interdependent cyber systems. Jointly provided to residents in one jurisdiction. An example of this is a country that can provide cyber services to its inhabitants thanks to large-scale sovereign cyber capabilities at the state and / or enterprise level. These interdependent cyber systems retain separate responsibilities, allowing each entity to take responsibility for parts of the system. You can also simply fall under the responsibility of the state, especially when trying to limit control of larger and more powerful companies such as Alphabet, Facebook, Amazon and Microsoft. Alternatively, the country can implement a private-public partner management mechanism, especially to manage the system as a single unit, making it difficult to see the boundaries of individual units within the system. For example, how would one institution or service provider within a highly interdependent whole cyber system stop providing services, negatively impacting complete service for all institutions and state residents? Is it? We believe it is possible for a country to give such a system a cyber personality.
4. Manifold-owned cyber system across multiple jurisdictions: Co-participating a highly interdependent cyber service set with multiple multinational corporations and / or residents of several jurisdictions, including jurisdiction, based on previous candidates Consider multiple weeks to serve in. It has complex and deeply nested roles and responsibilities. In some countries, such systems are eligible for a cyber personality, depending on the public's reliance on system services and the level of public impact when the services provided through the system are lost. I think you can think of it as.

Use and policy considerations

In addition to cyber personality candidates that require new legal action, as mentioned above, specific cases of behaviors that affect (or are actually performed) on highly interdependent cyber systems are the conceptual framework of cyber personality. Careful consideration should be given when setting. Globally, we were in a better position than we arrived a year later, given our strategic foresight and our “pre-thinking” of treatment for coronavirus infections. This treatise proposes that a country pre-thinks a cyber personality concept that will help determine how to respond when a particular country adopts such a position.

Below is a complete list of considerations that affect the rights and obligations of corporations that have a clear impact on future highly interdependent cyber systems that cannot function without the country and its societies.

- Injury: The nature of future highly interdependent cyber systems that exist in the physical world but manage data in the virtual world means that the potential for cyber system damage is extended to multiple domains. I

will. Cyber systems that are highly interdependent in the data domain can be held responsible for confidentiality breaches, integrity or access breaches, system or data corruption or corruption. In the physical world, it can harm all systems, including life-support systems that rely on networks for proper functioning. Interdependence is complicated, for example, when a component of a highly interdependent cyber system entity harms a component of another entity in the same system. Here either or both are designated as legal entities.

- Cyber-attacks (outside armed conflict): When highly interdependent cyber systems become victims of cyberattacks in the future, their rights and obligations depend on the existence of the organization, the degree of superiority of the organization and the "legal" recognition by the state. National and international levels.

When a highly interdependent cyber system is granted cyber privileges

The personality of the country in which the right can be exercised

These rights (and obligations-obligations to declare / declare to authorities)

(Serious breach) can be exercised prior to national jurisdiction.

You can also ask the administration for help.

For example, preventive protection and the following forms of service

Yet Sourcing and Security Monitoring. To such a result

The most basic expectation as a legal remedy is

A dictionary attack state of a cyber system with high interdependence.

- Cyber-attacks at the international level can bring demand. Protect the system by stakeholders 27 Retaliation for attack conditions or sanctions. Also, the customary law rules regarding national liability of a country are: Moved to "third country", a highly interdependent cyber system People with common interests can call them, we are providing support. 28 Due to the need and / or importance of advanced people

The interdependent cyber system we proposed The State also considers transferring these rules to such non-state actors. To support international law on national liability.

- Cyber-attack armed Conflicts depend on the qualifications of highly interdependent cyber systems. High level if applicable to critical infrastructure Protection 30 When the cyber system is used for private purposes only It qualifies and protects civilian objects. 31 Unfortunately When a highly interdependent cyber system is abused by a party to an armed group If there is a conflict, you can lose state. When it becomes a private sector When used for military purposes, it can be used for military purposes. 32 After an attack Cyber-attacks on military targets gain a military advantage.

Cyber systems with high interdependence are legal. Legal reason

Justifying protection is consensus on the neutrality of the state.

Highly interdependent cyber system or "digital" non

More interesting for a similar understanding You can qualify for a demilitarized zone based on an agreement.

Of the parties to the dispute.

- Obligation: Manufacturer or the system designer and the system itself must be determined strictly. The system demonstrates how much autonomy it has. Make sure that the responsibility for that action is not entirely the

responsibility of the designer Programmer or trainer (for A1). We also have an ongoing responsibility to maintain the system.

About the changes introduced in the function.

- **Liabilities:** In the event of system injuries, questions are raised about how to compensate for these injuries and when to raise funds to compensate the victims. Like corporations and businesses, future cyber systems with high interdependence can purchase liability insurance (or maintain self-insurance) and use trust funds to support injury costs. Users of highly interdependent cyber systems can be charged for services, and / or highly interdependent cyber systems can be funded by state collection, which is cost and service maintenance. And will support the operating funds.
- **Deputy and/or guardian:** the system Whenever you claim your event in court, you will be represented by a spokesperson in the same way as a human or corporate plaintiff or defendant. But the perceptual system is only the legal system, in the same way that deprived human groups were trying to organize order to secure their rights, either through the guild or through the guild. It is logical to do what you can ask for a representative in a company or politics, but also from your personality. Seeking political influence at the trade union or at the regional or state level. Choosing a guardian, the country may consider issues of industry-led or political motivation when assigned. The system is a conservation or advocacy group that acts as a responsible committee under the guidance of a system composed of relevant enterprises and political girders (eg, highly interdependent cyber system secretaries). Can be assigned by the parties to. Assigned to objects in the natural environment. Certain international organizations may be possible models.
- **International organization as a comparable concept:** related A hands-on solution for the jurisdiction of multiple systems International Administration and / or International Organization (IO) Obtained from international law and accordingly. So required pressure and / or specific IT issues international level is ICANN (Internet The mission of the company is as follows: Maintain an important database associated with namespaces and numbers Internet space) or ISO (International Organization for) Standardization, an association based on Swiss law) It is not managed as accurately as IO under international law. Therefore, practical ideas such as ICANN are proposed. is there Merged with the concept of IO in international law. This Explicitly suitable for sophisticated A1 complexes.

At least to establish an international organization Two countries in the form of international treaties are required. To The theme of this treaty is, of course, Participating countries' rights, obligations, and financing. You need to define the applicable area. Accurate, therefore Controlled, protected and protected interdependent cyber system It is displayed in IO.

Creation of an international entity for a particular height Interdependent cyber system are themselves Governance mechanism. Also, the integration of such law's Actual personality (e.g procedure, and representative question) It can be difficult. It can be solved in a similar way. An existing specific IO. On the other hand, the IO solution is clear A transparent framework based on national consensus Respond to legal and

practical requirements with gray areas. Finally, especially the benefits of establishing this international body are:

- (Digital) Human Rights Monitoring and Compliance

(For example, from the perspective of surveillance or big data AI)

- High level technology (eg Developing country);
- To maintain critical communication and information infrastructure Mechanism that works worldwide (backbone)
- Share responsibilities and share responsibilities. Sustainability (preventing environmental damage or Decarbonization and digestion promotion); and / or
- Mutual acceptance with common control over the central nervous system Technology (sophisticated, ultimately somewhat dangerous AI).

Conclusion

The information revolution has already brought about significant changes in most human lives and in what is considered normal and natural human behavior. The rate of such change continues to increase, and far more legal practices than during previous human history are considered only after the system has already been built. Not only the need for continuous updates of domestic computers, but also the development of cyber systems and features surpasses legal norms.

Through continuous discussion of the elements that make up the "cyber-attack" between the essence of cyber activities and the state, as well as information regulations 36) that reflect new uses and functions of information and communication technology.

Our treatise was created to help the country think ahead of the concept of cyber personality.

The example of environmental personality quoted above is such that the cyber personality is relevant to the legal processing of future highly interdependent cyber systems, is suitable for the purpose, and is still able to respond to the unexpected. We provide templates to consider if it is a viable means of guaranteeing sufficient flexibility. The development of relationships between humans and computing devices. Christopher Stone's first paper on environmental personality in 1972 was due to public awareness of environmental vulnerabilities and the need for protection based on their vital importance to human life support. It was in the very early stages of cognitive development, which is widespread in Japan. The process of widely embracing the notion of having to strike a balance between corporate interests, personal convenience and environmental protection has been long and, in some areas, still incomplete. However, we have similar cyber by emphasizing that incidents such as coronavirus infections are the essence of highly interdependent cyber services for the functioning of future societies and cannot be exchanged. I am thinking of accelerating the system process.

But the legal system to manage computer network measures

It has inevitably evolved, changed, and evolved significantly from its current state. Cyber personality may not be a concept in which the legal mechanism embraces the new reality of relying on the key humans of online services. However, the example of environmental legislation insists that this path can be seen as an important

means of solving practical problems in applying the existing legal system of cyber rights and responsibilities through cyber biomimetics. I am.

As we continue to study and recognize potential future scenarios, we can better endure. Environmental personalities for several reasons are not widely accepted or accepted. However, highly interdependent cyber systems can accommodate the cyber personalities that are essential to governments, societies, businesses and individuals.

The concept of cyber personality wasn't too far from the possibilities, especially as tools for managing it are already available, so it's worth discussing. The remaining issues are: Which country is bold enough to realize this concept, as some cyber systems develop importance and complexity that are considered worth managing under international law?

References

- [1] A Sophos Article 04.12v1.dNA, eight trends changing network security by James Lyne.
- [2] Cyber Security: Understanding Cyber Crimes- Sunit Belapure Nina Godbole
- [3] Computer Security Practices in Non Profit Organisations – A NetAction Report by Audrie Krause.
- [4] A Look back on Cyber Security 2012 by Luis corróns – Panda Labs.
- [5] International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 4, Issue 9, September-2013 Page nos.68 – 71 ISSN 2229-5518, “Study of Cloud Computing in HealthCare Industry “ by G.Nikhita Reddy, G.J.Ugander Reddy
- [6]. IEEE Security and Privacy Magazine – IEEECS “Safety Critical Systems – Next Generation “July/ Aug 2013.
- [7]. CIO Asia, September 3rd, H1 2013: Cyber security in malasia by Avanthi Kumar.
- [8] DBLP. Computer science bibliography. dblp.uni-trier.de. Last accessed May 10, 2018.
- [9] Z. Durumeric, M. Bailey, and J. A. Halderman. An Internet-wide view of Internet-wide scanning. In USENIX Security Symposium, pp. 65–78, San Diego, CA, 2014. USENIX Association.
- [10] Z. Durumeric, J. Kasten, M. Bailey, and J. A. Halderman. Analysis of the https certificate ecosystem. In ACM Inter-net Measurement Conference (IMC), pp. 291–304, NewYork, NY, USA, 2013. ACM.
- [11] E. Gal-Or and A. Ghose. The economic incentives for sharing security information. Information Systems Re-search, 16(2):186–208, 2005.
- [12] L. Gordon, M. Loeb, and W. Lucyshyn. Sharing informa-tion on computer systems security: An economic analy-sis. Journal of Accounting and Public Policy, 22(6):461–485, 2003.
- [13] C. Grajeda, F. Breitinger, and I. Baggili. Availability of datasets for digital forensics and what is missing. Digit. Investig., 22(S):S94–S105, Aug. 2017.
- [14] B. Henne, M. Koch, and M. Smith. On the aware-ness, control and privacy of shared photo metadata. In N. Christin and R. Safavi-Naini, editors, Financial Cryp-tography and Data Security, pp. 77–88, Berlin, Heidel-berg, 2014. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [15] M. H. Jhaveri, O. Cetin, C. Gáñan, T. Moore, and M. V.Eeten. Abuse reporting and the fight against cybercrime. ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR), 49(4):68, 2017.
- [16] H. Jiang, Y. Wang, K. Lee, and I. Rhee. Tackling bufferbloat in 3G/4G networks. In ACM IMC, pp. 329–342, New York, NY, USA, 2012. ACM.
- [17] T. Moore and R. Clayton. The consequence of non-

- cooperation in the fight against phishing. In APWG eCrime Researchers Summit, pp. 1–14. IEEE, 2008.
- [18] A. Newell, R. Potharaju, L. Xiang, and C. Nita-Rotaru. On the practicality of integrity attacks on document-level sentiment analysis. In ACM Workshop on Artificial Intel-ligent and Security Workshop, pp. 83–93, New York, NY, USA, 2014. ACM.
- [19] D. of Homeland Security. Information marketplace for policy and analysis of cyber-risk and trust. <https://www.impactcybertrust.org>. Last accessed May 10, 2018.
- [20] Y. Park, D. McCoy, and E. Shi. Understanding craigslist rental scams. In J. Grossklags and B. Preneel, editors, Financial Cryptography and Data Security, pp. 3–21, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2017. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [21] C. Sabottke, O. Suci, and T. Dumitras. Vulnerability disclosure in the age of social media: Exploiting twitter for predicting real-world exploits. In USENIX Security Symposium, pp. 1041–1056, Washington, D.C., 2015. USENIX Association
- [22] L. Wang, K. P. Dyer, A. Akella, T. Ristenpart, and T. Shrimpton. Seeing through network-protocol obfuscation. In ACM CCS, pp. 57–69, New York, NY, USA, 2015. ACM

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